

Modelling and deploying multi-energy flexibility: The energy lattice framework

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ABSTRACT

This work proposes a novel modelling framework and an associated optimization methodology for short-term operational planning to deploy multi-energy system (MES) flexibility, with application to district energy systems and participation in energy and frequency control ancillary services (FCAS). In this paper, the proposed flexibility framework, based on the concept of *multi-energy lattice*, models a MES by several energy layers, each one associated with a specific energy carrier. The identified energy layers are linked by specific conversion nodes associated with coupling devices that operate across several energy carriers. After illustrating in detail the main features of the multi-energy lattice methodology and, particularly, how it enables to clearly describe and quantify how flexibility arises from both single-layer and cross-layer energy balancing, different features of the concept of multi-energy flexibility are defined and discussed. An associated operational optimization methodology to deploy multi-energy flexibility in a market environment is then introduced. This methodology is based on a two-step mixed integer linear programming approach, namely, (i) definition of a multi-energy baseline to cope with the energy demand across multiple energy vectors and (ii) identification of flexibility margins and economic convenience to offer different FCAS by deploying multi-energy flexibility. The multi-energy lattice concept is then demonstrated on the Milan district heating system. This MES plant exploits its flexibility for participation in multiple FCAS markets besides day-ahead energy trading, and it is shown how the proposed methodology is able to optimize the flexibility arising from different devices and optimally combine these contributions across multiple energy layers for business case purposes, in line with the general theory of the multi-energy lattice.

1. Introduction

The increasing deployment of renewable energy sources (RES) in electric power systems worldwide is reducing the overall system flexibility, and poses many challenges in order to guaranty the safety and adequacy of the electricity supply [1–4]. In order to increase the RES hosting capacity, new technologies must provide some flexibility, both in terms of provision of active power reserve services to deal with RES volatility and net load ramping challenges [5,6]. Moreover, the increasing penetration of power electronics-connected voltage sources drastically reduced the system inertia, requiring frequency control ancillary services (FCAS), that can provide primary and secondary frequency response, and fast frequency response (FFR) [7].

Power system flexibility has gained great interest in the last decade and many research papers were published to deal with various aspect of the problem. An analysis of the power system flexibility requirements to integrate wind and solar energy across Europe is provided in [8], while advances in the flexibility provision at the system level and the definition of relevant flexibility metrics, were carried out in [9]. Lannoye et al. in [10] proposes new, ramp-based, flexibility metrics to assess the adequacy of future renewable-rich systems in terms of their flexibility requirements.

These works focus primarily on flexibility conceptualization and studies at the system-level. However, the shift towards distributed energy resources (DER) and energy decentralization, and digitalization, is

Abbreviations: CHP, Combined heat and power; DAM, Day ahead market; DER, Distributed energy resources; DH, District heating; EB, Electric boiler; EL, Energy layer; FAT, Full activation time; FCAS, Frequency control ancillary services; FCR, Frequency containment reserve; FFR, Fast frequency response; GB, Gas boiler; a/mFRR, Automatic/manual frequency restoration reserve; HP, Heat pump; HS, Heat storage; MES, Multi-energy system; MILP, Mixed integer linear programming; MW_e, Megawatt: electrical power; MW_t, Megawatt: thermal power; RES, Renewable energy sources; SRMC, Short run marginal cost.

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Notation**Indices**

b	Index for storage devices $B \subseteq \mathcal{R}$
d	Index for demand D
\mathcal{E}_x	Index for energy vectors \mathcal{E}
g	Index for conversion devices $\mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathcal{R}$
k	Index for services S
r	Index for devices \mathcal{R}

Sets

B	Set of storage devices, $b, B \subseteq \mathcal{R}$
$\{D\}_{\mathcal{E}_x}$	Set of demands associated with energy layer \mathcal{E}_x , d
\mathcal{E}	Set of energy vectors, \mathcal{E}_x
\mathcal{G}	Set of conversion devices, $g, \mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathcal{R}$
\mathcal{R}	Set of MES devices, r
\mathcal{R}_k	Set of devices participating in service k , $\mathcal{R}_k \subseteq \mathcal{R}$
$\{S\}_{\mathcal{E}_x}$	Set of services associated with energy layer \mathcal{E}_x , k

Variables

$e_{b,t}$	State of charge of storage b
f_t^{Ph}	Physical flexibility
$f_t^{Op,+/-}$	Operational flexibility
$f_t^{Cb,+/-}$	Carrier balancing flexibility
$f_t^{Mp,+/-}$	Market product flexibility
$f_t^{Ec,+/-}$	Economic flexibility
$f_t^{+/-}$	Market flexibility
$p_{r,t}$	Power output of resource r
$p_{b,t}^{+/-}$	Power charge/discharge of storage b
$p_t^{imp/exp}$	Power import/export of the MES
$\Delta p_{r,t}$	Power deviation of resource r to provide various services
$z_{r,t}$	On/off status of a device r
$z_{b,t}^{+/-}$	Binary variable indicating charging/discharging status of storage b
z_t^{imp}	Binary variable indicating power import/export status of MES
ω_t	Energy layer losses

Parameters

$\alpha_g^{\varepsilon_y, \varepsilon_x}$	Loss factor of device g , converting energy ε_y To ε_x
$\sigma_g^{\varepsilon_y, \varepsilon_x}$	Conversion efficiency of device g , converting energy ε_x To ε_y
ψ_k	Call length of service k
$\eta_b^{+/-}$	Charging/discharging efficiency of storage b
$\rho_{S_k,t}$	Price of service S_k
ρ^{exp}	Power export price
ρ_d	Demand fulfilment price
C_r	Unitary cost of operating device r
C^{imp}	Cost of power import
C^λ	Cost of curtailment
$\bar{e}_b / \underline{e}_b$	Maximum/minimum energy limit of storage b
$\bar{p}_r / \underline{p}_r$	Maximum/minimum power limit of device r
$\bar{p}_b^{+/-}$	Maximum charge/discharge rate of storage b
$\bar{p}^{imp/exp}$	Maximum power import/export limit of the MES
$p_{d,t}$	Power demand requirement d
p_k	Minimum power required to participate in service k
$r_r^{+/-}$	Ramp up/down of device r
Δt	Duration of time interval (time resolution)
$t_k^{a/d}$	Full activation/deactivation time for service k

opening up new opportunities for DER, and distributed energy systems, in active distribution networks to provide flexibility and grid services. This topic is relatively little explored, see for example [11], whereby the

concept of the *power node* has been used to elaborate on demand-side flexibility and on which several efforts are currently emerging (see e.g. [12]).

On the other hand, the development of distributed energy systems is also creating a fertile background for the advent of the so-called (distributed) multi-energy systems (MES) [13], which are based on the integrated operation of different energy vectors, sectors and networks (e.g., electricity, heat, cooling, gas, hydrogen, etc.) [14]. MES integration will play a crucial role in the decarbonisation of the whole energy system and towards a net-zero economy. The key emerging benefits from MES lie in their capability to provide flexibility to the power system, which is inherent in their virtual storage options coming from thermo-chemical features, e.g., thermal inertia in buildings and heat networks, linepack flexibility from gas networks, and so on [13,15]. This is particularly relevant to district energy systems that are multi-energy by nature and in which suitable centralized optimization, control and commercial strategies [16] may be readily developed to deploy MES flexibility for the provision of market and system services [17].

The most known modelling approach for MES is the so-called *energy hub* proposed by Geidl and Andersson in [18,19], which first provided a general representation paradigm for MES, enabling abstracting from a specific physical system into a mathematical input-output representation of the interactions occurring among different energy system component across several energy carriers. Thus, the energy hub model can be generally used as a reference to represent all the energy flows inside a MES and its external interactions with energy networks, by focussing on the links between *supply* and *demand* through conversion units. This logical representation has its natural counterpart in the matrix-based mathematical formalization which corresponds to highly nonconvex optimization models [20]. The energy hub has been deployed extensively in the literature to model MES [21–27]. Gabrielli et al in [21] presented a MILP operational model suitable for MES design while capturing impacts of seasonal energy storage. Research in [22] aimed to extend the energy hub suitability for load flow analysis in coupled district energy networks. The role of energy hub for decentralized energy systems at the neighbourhood level is studied in [23]. A general model for energy hub economic dispatch is considered in [24]. The impact of ice storage on the operation of energy hub for integration of renewables and demand response is elaborated in [25]. However, all of these works are only focused of energy markets and lacks modelling of the energy hub participation in provision of ancillary services. To this end, a techno-economic model considering multi service is presented by the authors in [26]. Furthermore, a more recent work [27] proposed a three-stage robust scheduling approach to optimize multi-market participation considering uncertainty. However, both of these works [26,27] only considers electrical vector and are not able to fully exploit the flexibility available in multi-energy hub.

Chicco et al. in [13] have recently introduced the concept of *multi-energy node* as an integration and generalization of the notions of *power node* [2], describing system flexibility from the point of view of a local electrical system, and *energy hub* [2], describing the multi-energy feature of a local system. In particular, the main limitation of the *power node* framework lies in the central role played by the electrical carrier, which deeply impacts the system management. This extension, provided in [13], fully supports multi-energy modelling and also provides a number of operational constraints which generalize those proposed in [2], to single or multiple distributed (multi)-energy-nodes, including the role of networks as flexibility enablers and constraints. The multi-energy node effectively represents how a generic MES, and its internal multi-energy conversions and storage operations, interacts with the electrical network, with focus on the flexibility that the MES can provide to the rest of the system. The electrical flexibility provided to the external power system is essentially enabled by several multi-energy flexibility features, that are internal to the MES, including energy arbitrage (shifting) across multiple carriers, time arbitrage, multi-energy service curtailment, etc. [13], as mentioned earlier.

Fig. 1. Important factor to determine MES market participation.

However, the energy hub and multi-energy node frameworks are basically focused on physical modelling and lack a general degree of abstraction, that may be suitable to represent and support the development of different business model opportunities from participation in electricity markets, provision of demand management services, etc.

MES modelling was investigated in several papers, for instance [13] and others have provided a general mathematical framework to assess the potential flexibility, most noticeably [2]. However, the focus has primarily been posed on the modelling of the *physical* processes associated with the relevant energy transformations, then extended to operational and economic aspects. For example to satisfy local demand by suitable management policies [28,29]. However, very limited attention (see for example [30]) has been paid to the modelling of the flexibility embedded in MES with the aim of trading ancillary services, and in particular FCAS. In general, there is no modelling and analysis framework that systematically describes MES flexibility and its application to provision of FCAS, considering all the technical, economic and commercial aspects of the relevant constraints and opportunities. In fact, the market participation potential of the MES may be limited by the device constraints (e.g., power rating, ramp rate, state of charge, etc.), multi-energy vector coupling (i.e., interaction between two energy vectors) constraints, market requirements (e.g., activation time, duration, etc.) and flexibility deployment cost (e.g., fuel cost, lost opportunity, etc.), as illustrated in Fig. 1.

Based on this background, this paper presents the work that has been carried out in the context of the European project H2020 MAGNITUDE (n. 774309). This work proposes a novel modelling framework and optimization methodology to quantify and deploy the multi-faceted flexibility available in a MES, with particular a focus on short-term operational planning of district energy system applications. The proposed flexibility framework is based on the novel concept of *multi-energy lattice*, whereby several energy layers, each one associated to a specific energy carrier, interact to each other and with the external world. Interactions denote physical carrier flows within the MES or toward the external world. In the second case, interactions denote energy carrier flows and business models related to services or demand provision. Each element represented in the methodology is identified and it is meant as a possible source of flexibility, supporting potential optimization opportunities.

This paper illustrates in detail the main features of the energy lattice framework and the associated operational optimization methodol-

ogy, which is based on mixed integer linear programming (MILP) and composed of two steps, namely: (i) multi-energy participation to cope with the energy demand across multiple energy vectors and (ii) identification of flexibility margins and economic convenience to offer FCAS. The relevant case studies applied to a real-world district heating (DH) plant in Milan, Italy, also demonstrating the power and effectiveness of the proposed multi-energy lattice approach and associated optimization methodologies. Hence, by providing a novel analysis framework whose lenses can clearly expose benefits and barriers for MES in providing system services (and FCAS in particular) to different markets. Our contributions, and novel elements, can create impacts in different respects, including to inform the ongoing policy and regulatory debates with regards to flexibility, grid services markets, distributed energy systems, and multi-energy systems.

The case study shows how multi-energy flexibility could first of all be deployed for day-ahead satisfaction of the heat network energy demand, and day-ahead electricity market participation facilitated by day-ahead gas supply. Gas supply provides great flexibility to both the electricity and heat energy layers, based on, respectively, gas-to-electricity and gas-to-heat conversion devices. Then, we illustrate and assess how, besides the flexibility margins made available by the day-ahead operation (for both upward and downward operation), additional multi-energy flexibility could be deployed by shifting across multiple energy vectors [31], particularly via electricity-to-heat devices (e.g., electric boilers). Most importantly, we also discuss how even gas-to-heat technologies are able to *indirectly* provide flexibility on the electrical carrier/energy layer. This further highlights the importance and power of the multi-energy lattice framework in fully and clearly capturing all the interactions across different energy layers to unlock multi-energy flexibility. By doing so, we are thus able to translate the general, theoretical flexibility concepts and modelling framework into potential deployment of real market services, subject to real-world technical and market constraints. In particular, the Milan DH plant allows us to flesh out all the complex technical features associated with MES flexibility, and particularly how energy demand of one energy vector might influence the overall plant flexibility. Further techno-economic considerations are then made on the value associated with MES flexibility as potentially extracted from participation in multiple, different FCAS markets. In particular, the main contribution of the paper are as follows:

- Novel multi-energy lattice framework to model MES flexibility, with focus on facilitating provision of multiple market services.
- Detailed and novel categorization of MES flexibility features to address both technical and commercial aspects.
- Two-step optimization methodology to deploy MES flexibility for short-term operational planning.
- Modelling of simultaneous participation in energy & frequency control ancillary service markets.
- Demonstration of the methodology on a real-world case study, namely, the Milan district heating system.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: the general aspects of the multi-energy lattice framework and flexibility feature characterization is outlined in Section 2. Section 3 introduces the two-step optimization methodology for flexibility deployment in the context of short-term operational planning and participation in energy and FCAS. Section 4 describes the real-world case study, which is based on the Milan DH plant. The discussion of the results is comprehensively presented in Section 5. Section 6 reports conclusions and future work.

2. The multi-energy lattice framework

2.1. Multi-energy lattice

In its more general understanding, the modelling of a MES requires the ability to represent the physical processes associated to

the transformations, from one carrier to another, performed by resources/devices/plant, [14]. In the recent years, modelling features concerning the interactions with the external environment require to couple the (“traditional”) physical transfer of energy carrier with the related business rules posed by markets, or by demand. For instance, these refer to the access to the energy markets, to recruit or sell energy resources, and to exploit (multi-energy) demand management. MES models, where physical and business features are combined together, are becoming powerful optimization means, taking advantage of the opportunities at the physical level as well as at the business one.

The *multi-energy lattice* framework proposed here aims at developing a common framework to provide an essential techno-economic modelling support for the exploitation of FCAS. This is relevant to both MES operators, who can optimize the utilization and deployment of their resources for business case purposes, as well as system operators, who increasingly look for reliable and new sources of flexibility. In more detail, the energy Lattice framework defined in this section is mainly designed for short term (e.g., day ahead) operational planning, where units are economically dispatched to satisfy the expected multi-energy demand and then their flexibility is deployed for FCAS provision. This can then support the MES operator to optimize the daily/weekly production and thus also the business case for MES partaking in a wide range of electrical ancillary services.

2.2. Multi-energy lattice: main features

Multi-energy lattice framework aims to represent with a certain level of abstraction the energetic transformation processes in a MES that involve several energy carriers. This enables the framework to identify the different market opportunities, where the MES can acquire the energy carriers required for the relevant conversion and production processes and distribute the energy carriers after the relevant transformations inside the plant. In contrast with the multi-energy node and the energy hub models (focused on the operational modelling of conversion devices), the main strength of the proposed multi-energy lattice framework is its potential to set a clear interface with respect to the multi-energy services, especially FCAS, and demand supplied by the MES across several energy carriers.

The framework represents a MES as a lattice constituted by a set of *energy layers* (EL) connected by *conversion nodes*. Each energy layer is associated with an energy carrier consisting of a set of energy *conversion* devices (that carry out the energy transformation), energy storage, and demand profile. Conversion devices are represented by grey-box models, that is: models are based on physical laws, but parameters are set through real data, or by statistical methods, to ensure an optimal fit with the actual system. The energy is imported/exported through external networks and converted by suitable conversion nodes across pairs of energy layers, physically performed by conversion devices (e.g., gas-to-heat, gas-to-power, etc.).

Relevant technical/market (external) *services* can then be provided to the energy layer by controlling the energy import/export by leveraging the flexibility of conversion devices and storage to meet energy demand. The current version of the energy lattice framework supports the MES modelling where the network constraints are not binding (e.g. see [14]).

There can be multiple services associated with an energy layer \mathcal{E}_x , $\{S = \{S_1, S_2, \dots, S_K\}\}_{\mathcal{E}_x}$. Each service (S) can be for “import”, “export”, or “dual-mode”: the import services require increase in the import (or decrease in the export) of an energy carrier, export services require increase in the export (or decrease in the import) of an energy carrier, while dual-mode may require both directions of energy flows. There can also be multiple demands associated to the energy layer \mathcal{E}_x , $\{D = \{D_1, D_2, \dots, D_N\}\}_{\mathcal{E}_x}$. Each demand in the set D represents an “export” of the relevant energy carrier from the MES, thus it is also associated with a payment.

In contrast to the multi-energy hub and multi-energy node models introduced above which focus on the physical modelling of de-

VICES, the energy lattice methodology is designed to assess and support the multi-market participation and relevant business case development while maintaining a general degree of abstraction. In particular, the model presented here is developed for operational planning assessment. The expected short-term (e.g., day ahead) multi-energy demand is fulfilled in an economic manner and then utilizes the available flexibility to participate in ancillary services. Some existing frameworks, for example [32], carry out similar functions, supporting a wider set of tasks like goal identification, setting of operational strategies, configuration of the system, definition of scenarios, system control and modelling of the economics. The energy lattice methodology does not cover a so wide range of abilities. However, energy lattice methodology supports MES operator to optimize the daily/weekly production to meet demand and facing the widest set of ancillary services, ensuring the right balancing across the energy carriers at the finest level of detail.

Let us consider as an exemplification of the energy lattice framework a MES consisting of only a CHP: the complete CHP gas engine with its key features are illustrated using the multi-energy lattice framework in Fig. 2. In the *gas layer*, the fuel is acquired from the gas day-ahead market (gDAM), and this represents an *import service*. The CHP converts the gas into heat and electricity through conversion nodes of $\sigma_{CHP}^{gas,heat}$ and $\sigma_{CHP}^{gas,elect}$, respectively. In the *heat layer*, the heat generated by the CHP is used to fulfil heat demand (i.e., D_1, \dots, D_N) requirement to generate revenues. It should be noted that the operating point of the CHP is thus constrained by the heat demand. In the *electricity layer* the electrical power produced by the CHP can be used to generate revenues in two ways: i) by fulfilling the electricity demand (i.e., D_1, \dots, D_M) requirement, and ii) by exporting electricity to the external network and thus providing a range of services, e.g., energy in electricity DAM (eDAM), FCAS, etc.

The generic energy layer \mathcal{E}_x is depicted in Fig. 3, which includes energy layer services, demand, conversion and storage devices, *losses* (ω) and *demand-shedding* (λ). Services and demand model the exchange of the physical energy carrier between MES and external entities which implies an economic transaction (e.g., energy market participation, bilateral agreements, etc). In the example depicted in Fig. 3, $\{S_1\}_{\mathcal{E}_x}$ is an import service, $\{S_2\}_{\mathcal{E}_x}$ is an export service, while $\{S_K\}_{\mathcal{E}_x}$ is a dual-mode (import/export) service. Demand is an unidirectional (supply) service to an external entity, which could also be represented by a number of instances $\{D = \{D_1, D_2, \dots, D_N\}\}_{\mathcal{E}_x}$ (e.g., for DH customers) and relevant payments.

2.3. Multi-energy lattice model of MES flexibility

The flexibility owned by a MES, accounted against a given baseline, can be exploited to provide extra-services like FCAS in the electricity markets [33]. In the context of the electricity grid, operational flexibility can be defined as “the technical ability of a power system unit to modulate electrical power feed-in to the grid and/or power out-feed from the grid over time” [2]. Generally, this definition can be directly applied to any energy carrier, e.g., to gas and heat. However, calculation of flexibility taking into account the multi-energy transformations occurring in a MES requires a careful analysis of resulting operational margins within and across multi energy layers. In this respect, an early definition of electricity flexibility emerging from MES was provided in [33] under the concept of “energy shifting potential”. In this case, electricity flexibility is defined as the “maximum possible reduction in electrical network input”, which is effectively an upper bound proxy for upward flexibility. A general definition of *MES flexibility* has been recently provided in [13] as “the technical ability of a system to regulate multi-energy supply, demand and power flows subject to steady-state and dynamic constraints and while operating within predefined/desired boundary regions for certain energy vectors”. However, this definition does not take into account the dynamic (inter-temporal) aspects of MES flexibility. A quantitative definition of electricity flexibility, which also incorporates dynamic (inter-temporal) aspects, was introduced in [34] by using the capacity-ramp-energy met-

Fig. 2. Canonical example of multi-energy lattice for a gas combined heat and power plant (CHP): energy layer (EL) includes gas (yellow), electricity (blue) and heat (red); the conversion nodes representing transformation from gas to heat (red line) and gas to electricity (blue line).

Fig. 3. Generic energy layer schematics.

rics. This triplet can also generally support the *dynamic* representation of multi-energy flexibility in a MES, and can be further broken down to represent the flexibility direction, that is, for “increasing power” (upward, (+)) and “decreasing power” (downward, (-)), respectively. Hence, flexibility can emerge from individual devices as well as aggregation of several devices (see [2] for electricity systems and [13] for MES).

In the multi-energy lattice framework, flexibility essentially results from appropriately balancing (ideally optimising) the different flexibility components in each energy layer and across multiple layers, with the aim of providing external services while supplying the multi-energy demand. Such balance may be carried out in different ways looking at the specific flexibility contributions across the different layers and avoiding trivial compensations.

Let us consider first the flexibility balancing mechanisms applied to just one energy layer \mathcal{E}_x , as depicted by the relevant directions of energy flow in the three graphs in Fig. 4. In Fig. 4-(a), the *import* service $\{S_1\}_{\mathcal{E}_x}$ imports power and is balanced by flexibility contributions as follows: increasing energy conversion from energy layer \mathcal{E}_x to other layers, decreasing energy conversion from other energy layers to \mathcal{E}_x , and charging storage. In Fig. 4-(b), the *export* service $\{S_2\}_{\mathcal{E}_x}$ is balanced by reducing energy conversion from \mathcal{E}_x to other energy layers, increasing energy conversion from other energy layers to \mathcal{E}_x , and discharging storage. The dual-mode service $\{S_3\}_{\mathcal{E}_x}$, in Fig. 4-(c), can be split into two (mutually exclusive) components, whereby the balancing consists in applying in turn the balancing schemes set for import and export services as proposed in Fig. 4-(a) and Fig. 4-(b), respectively. For example, in case of electricity layer, import and export services could correspond to lower and raise frequency response contingency services, respectively. Whereas the dual mode service corresponds to a market with dual power flow such as energy or frequency regulation services.

Now, let us generalize the balancing of flexibility contributions across *several* energy layers. To do so, let us first consider the import service $\{S_1\}_{\mathcal{E}_x}$ associated with the energy layer \mathcal{E}_x , as shown in Fig. 5. The energy layers \mathcal{E}_x and \mathcal{E}_w are linked together by conversion node $\sigma_{g1}^{x,w}$, i.e., a conversion device that convert energy \mathcal{E}_x into \mathcal{E}_w . The energy layers \mathcal{E}_x and \mathcal{E}_y are linked together by conversion node $\sigma_{g2}^{y,x}$, whereby

the input acquired by g_2 in \mathcal{E}_y generates an output in \mathcal{E}_x . As, discussed above, the import service $\{S_1\}_{\mathcal{E}_x}$ can therefore be delivered by i) charging storage in energy layer \mathcal{E}_x ; ii) increasing energy flow to conversion node g_1 and thus increasing energy production of \mathcal{E}_w , which may be balanced through charging storage of layer \mathcal{E}_w or increasing energy export $\{S_E\}_{\mathcal{E}_w}$; iii) decreasing energy flow from conversion node g_2 and thus decreasing energy consumption of \mathcal{E}_y , which may be balanced through decrease in energy import $\{S_E\}_{\mathcal{E}_y}$ or increase charging storage in layer \mathcal{E}_y .

Similarly, the export service $\{S_2\}_{\mathcal{E}_x}$, with reference to Fig. 6 is associated to the energy layer \mathcal{E}_x , and may be provided by i) discharging storage of energy layer \mathcal{E}_x ; ii) decreasing energy flow from conversion node g_1 and thus reducing energy production of \mathcal{E}_w , which may be balanced through discharging storage or decreasing energy export $\{S_E\}_{\mathcal{E}_w}$; iii) increasing energy flow from conversion node g_2 and thus increasing energy consumption of \mathcal{E}_y , which may be balanced through increasing energy import $\{S_E\}_{\mathcal{E}_y}$ or discharging storage in layer \mathcal{E}_y . The analysis for the balancing of dual-mode service, as illustrated in the case of single energy-layer, can be derived by the combination of the import and export components.

Flexibility in the context of the multi-energy lattice operation, as addressed here, thus results from power modulations of single device, or an aggregation of devices that, by linking multiple energy layers, provide flexibility *across* all energy layers (that is, energy vectors) that are pertinent to the MES. In particular, flexibility can be extracted from the energy layer/carrier from which it may be more “convenient” or even “optimal”, which may be measured and assessed in different ways depending on the context and purpose (for example, aiming at maximum variation of a specific energy carrier, or at lowest overall cost, etc.). Flexibility is of course also subject to all physical and operational matters occurring in the MES, besides other potential techno-economic or potential constraints.

2.4. Flexibility feature characterization

In many occasions, flexibility is treated in a simplified manner, with multiple aspects of it being disregarded. Therefore, given the discussion presented in Section 2.3, this paper also try to provide a comprehensive view of flexibility and propose a categorization of *flexibility features* that are sorted hierarchically in a bottom up perspective, from the physical/operational matters up to the market regulatory ones, as follows:

- *Physical*: intrinsic modulation capability for an energy carrier (and, in particular, electricity) which is potentially owned by the MES (spanning all the technically feasible operating range).

Fig. 4. Energy layer flexibility: provision of different services.

Fig. 5. Cross-carrier flexibility balancing for an “import” service.

Fig. 6. Cross-carrier flexibility balancing for an “export” service.

- **Operational:** modulation capability for an energy carrier that the MES can provide with respect to (starting from) a given operating point and within its technically feasible operating region.
- **Carrier-balancing:** operational flexibility for an energy carrier, reduced by the constraints imposed by the other energy carriers through conversion nodes.
- **Market-product:** carrier-balancing flexibility subject to market product constraints, e.g., maximum allowed activation time, minimum service duration, etc.
- **Economic:** flexibility that the MES operator can offer at a given cost for a specific service and accounting for MES economic objectives (to be optimized).
- **Market:** economic flexibility cleared and accepted by the market given the market requirements and other offers.

The relationship between different flexibility features is represented in Fig. 7, via Venn diagram.

2.4.1. Physical flexibility

Physical flexibility ($\{f_{r,t}^{Ph}\}_{\mathcal{E}_x}$) of a device (conversion or storage) r represents the maximum flexibility available on the energy vector $\mathcal{E}_x \in \mathcal{E}$ and is quantified by its operational range as:

$$\left\{ f_{r,t}^{Ph} = z_{r,t} (\bar{p}_r - \underline{p}_r) \right\}_{\mathcal{E}_x} \quad \forall r \in \mathcal{R} \quad (1)$$

where, $z_{r,t}$ is the on/off status of a device r in device set \mathcal{R} , in time step t , while \bar{p}_r and \underline{p}_r , are the maximum and minimum operating limits of a device r for the energy vector \mathcal{E}_x , respectively. The on/off status in the above equation denotes that if a device is offline then it cannot provide any flexibility.

Fig. 7. Venn diagram representing the relationship between the different aspect of flexibility.

Therefore, the physical flexibility associated with energy layer \mathcal{E}_x of the MES can be represented by the summation of the physical flexibility of all the devices r in the MES device set \mathcal{R} :

$$\left\{ f_t^{Ph} = \sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}} f_{r,t}^{Ph} \right\}_{\mathcal{E}_x} \quad \forall r \in \mathcal{R} \quad (2)$$

2.4.2. Operational flexibility

The operational flexibility classifies the physical flexibility of a device into upward/downward ($\{f_{r,t}^{Op,+/-}\}_{\mathcal{E}_x}$) components available to the energy vector \mathcal{E}_x . The operational flexibility of a device can be expressed

as:

$$f_{r,t}^{Ph} = f_{r,t}^{Op,+} + f_{r,t}^{Op,-} \quad \forall r \in \mathcal{R} \quad (3)$$

Furthermore, the upward/downward operational flexibility of the conversion devices ($\mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathcal{R}$) can be expressed as the function of the device operating point ($p_{g,t}$) as:

$$\left\{ f_{g,t}^{Op,+} = z_{g,t} (\bar{p}_g - p_{g,t}) \right\}_{\mathcal{E}_x} \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{G} \quad (4)$$

$$\left\{ f_{g,t}^{Op,-} = z_{g,t} (p_{g,t} - \underline{p}_g) \right\}_{\mathcal{E}_x} \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{G} \quad (5)$$

In the above equations ($\bar{p}_g - p_{g,t}$) and ($p_{g,t} - \underline{p}_g$) are the power head-room and foot-room of the device g , respectively. The upward/downward operational flexibility of the storage devices ($\mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{R}$) depends both upon power and energy head/foot room as:

$$\left\{ f_{b,t}^{Op,+} = \min \left\{ \bar{p}_b - (p_{b,t}^+ - p_{b,t}^-), \frac{\eta_b^- (\bar{e}_b - e_{b,t})}{\Delta t} \right\} \right\}_{\mathcal{E}_x} \quad \forall b \in \mathcal{B} \quad (6)$$

$$\left\{ f_{b,t}^{Op,-} = \min \left\{ p_{b,t}^+ - \bar{p}_b - \bar{p}_b \cdot \frac{e_{b,t}}{\eta_b^+ \Delta t} \right\} \right\}_{\mathcal{E}_x} \quad \forall b \in \mathcal{B} \quad (7)$$

$$\{ \underline{e}_b \leq e_{b,t} + \Delta e_{b,t} \leq \bar{e}_b \}_{\mathcal{E}_x} \quad \forall b \in \mathcal{B} \quad (8)$$

where, \bar{p}_b^+/\bar{p}_b^- , $p_{b,t}^+/p_{b,t}^-$, η_b^+/η_b^- , $\bar{e}_b/e_{b,t}$ and $e_{b,t}$ represent maximum charge/discharge rate, charge/discharge power, charging/discharging efficiency, maximum/minimum energy limit and state of charge of storage, respectively. The parameter Δt is the interval for which the operational flexibility is to be determined. Furthermore, provision of flexibility margins in a storage device is a difficult task due to intertemporal constraint, which could lead to infeasible baseline operating scheduling. This is avoided by splitting the storage energy into two components dedicated to the baseline ($e_{b,t}$) and the flexibility service provision ($\Delta e_{b,t}$). The energy contribution for the provision of flexibility can be obtained as: $\Delta e_{b,t} = \frac{f_{b,t}^{Op,-}}{\eta_b^+} \Delta t - \eta_b^- f_{b,t}^{Op,+} \Delta t - \Delta e_{b,t}^{\text{loss}}$.

2.4.3. Carrier-balancing flexibility

In a MES the energy vectors are coupled and cannot be viewed independently, therefore the operational flexibility available to the energy vector \mathcal{E}_x is also impacted by the constraints of other energy vectors \mathcal{E}_y . For a conversion device $g \in \mathcal{G}$ coupling energy vectors \mathcal{E}_x and \mathcal{E}_y , the upward/downward carrier balancing flexibility ($\{f_{g,t}^{Cb,+/-}\}_{\mathcal{E}_x}$) available to vector \mathcal{E}_x can be expressed as:

$$\left\{ f_{g,t}^{Cb,+/-} \right\}_{\mathcal{E}_x} \leq \left\{ f_{g,t}^{Op,+/-} \right\}_{\mathcal{E}_x} \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{G} \quad (9)$$

$$\left\{ f_{g,t}^{Cb,+/-} \right\}_{\mathcal{E}_x} \leq \left\{ f_{g,t}^{Op,+/-} : \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} p_{g,t} \leq \bar{p}^{\text{imp}}, \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} p_{g,t} \leq \bar{p}^{\text{exp}} \right\}_{\mathcal{E}_y} \sigma_g^{\mathcal{E}_y, \mathcal{E}_x} + \alpha_g^{\mathcal{E}_y, \mathcal{E}_x} \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{G} \quad (10)$$

The above equations state that the carrier balancing flexibility available to energy vector \mathcal{E}_x is not only limited by the respective operational flexibility but also by transformed operational flexibility of conversion device g for energy vector \mathcal{E}_y . In Eq. (10), the quantity $\{f_{g,t}^{Op,+/-} : \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} p_{g,t} \leq \bar{p}^{\text{imp}}, \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} p_{g,t} \leq \bar{p}^{\text{exp}}\}_{\mathcal{E}_y}$ is the operational flexibility of a device subjected to the operational range of energy vector \mathcal{E}_y , $\bar{p}^{\text{imp}}/\bar{p}^{\text{exp}}$ represents the maximum power import/export limit of the MES, $\sigma_g^{\mathcal{E}_y, \mathcal{E}_x}$ is conversion efficiency and $\alpha_g^{\mathcal{E}_y, \mathcal{E}_x}$ is the loss of the conversion device g .

2.4.4. Market-product flexibility

Ancillary services generally require a number of constraints on flexibility. For instance, the generic service S_k has to be provided in a pre-defined full activation time (t_k^a) so the flexibility provided by a cluster of resources ($\mathcal{R}_k \subseteq \mathcal{R}$) to participate in market service is limited by carrier balancing flexibility, in (11), and by ramp up/down capabilities ($r_r^{+/-}$), to fulfil market full activation time (FAT), as represented in (12).

$$\left\{ f_{r,t}^{Mp,+/-} \leq f_{r,t}^{Cb,+/-} \right\}_{\mathcal{E}_x} \quad \forall r \in \mathcal{R} \quad (11)$$

$$\left\{ f_{r,t}^{Mp,+/-} \leq r_r^{+/-} t_k^a \right\}_{\mathcal{E}_x} \quad \forall r \in \mathcal{R}_k \quad (12)$$

Furthermore, the participation of MES in different markets is further restricted by (13), ensuring that the devices have collectively enough ramping capabilities to participate in a market as:

$$\left\{ f_{S_k,t}^{Mp,+/-} \leq \sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}_k} f_{r,t}^{Mp,+/-} \right\}_{\mathcal{E}_x} \quad \forall S_k \in \{S\}_{\mathcal{E}_x} \quad (13)$$

2.4.5. Economic flexibility

The economic flexibility ($\{f_{r,t}^{\text{Ec},+/-}\}_{\mathcal{E}_x}$) identifies the device flexibility to face a service while considering economic aspects. A device will only participate in a given service if the revenues are greater than the cost of delivering that service as expressed as:

$$\left\{ f_{r,t}^{\text{Ec},+/-} \leq f_{r,t}^{Mp,+/-} : (z_{r,t} f_{r,t}^{Op,+/-} (p_{S_k,t} - C_r) \geq 0) \right\}_{\mathcal{E}_x} \quad \forall r \in \mathcal{R}_k \quad (14)$$

where \mathcal{R}_k represents the set of resources that can be dispatched to participate in service $\{S_k\}_{\mathcal{E}_x}$, C_r is the unitary cost of operating device r and $p_{S_k,t}$ is the short run marginal cost (SRMC) of the service $\{S_k\}_{\mathcal{E}_x}$. Therefore, the economic flexibility of the MES to provide $\{S_k\}_{\mathcal{E}_x}$ service can be identified as:

$$\left\{ f_{S_k,t}^{\text{Ec},+/-} \leq \sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}_k} f_{r,t}^{\text{Ec},+/-} \right\}_{\mathcal{E}_x} \quad \forall S_k \in \{S\}_{\mathcal{E}_x} \quad (15)$$

2.4.6. Market flexibility

Finally, the market flexibility ($\{f_{r,t}^{+/-}\}_{\mathcal{E}_x}$) expresses the amount of flexibility accepted by the market (at settlement stage) and this is what a device is obliged to provide in time interval t , expressed as:

$$\left\{ f_{r,t}^{+/-} \leq f_{r,t}^{\text{Ec},+/-} \right\}_{\mathcal{E}_x} \quad \forall r \in \mathcal{R} \quad (16)$$

The MES obligation to participate in services $\{S_k\}_{\mathcal{E}_x}$ is:

$$\left\{ f_{S_k,t}^{+/-} \leq \sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}_k} f_{r,t}^{+/-} \right\}_{\mathcal{E}_x} \quad \forall S_k \in \{S\}_{\mathcal{E}_x} \quad (17)$$

3. Modelling framework for optimal flexibility deployment

The modelling framework presented below describes a relevant optimization tool to carry out the techno-economic analysis of MES while participating in multi-energy and multi-service markets by deploying the multi-energy flexibility features presented above. The framework refers to short-term horizon, one or more days, with 15 min/30 min/one hour time resolution. This optimization tool links the main multi-energy lattice features, as proposed in Section 2.2, with the features of an optimization modelling language. First of all, the optimization tool supports the association with the energy layers, (market) services, demand(s), and devices through suitable terms. Specific bounding constraints are set to define the variable domains, as well as the device operating interactions. Balancing constraint equations are set to guarantee energy carrier balance. Services and demand(s) terms are defined to represent both energy carrier flows and prices/costs related to the economic transactions. Economic terms are appropriately combined in the optimization objective function. The device operational costs are modelled, when relevant, by the import fuel or energy carrier cost for a relevant service.

Fig. 8. Block diagram of the two-step methodology adopted in the presented work.

Each energy carrier managed in the MES is identified by a \mathcal{E}_x , and the set of all energy carriers can be defined as:

$$\mathcal{E} = \{\mathcal{E}_1, \mathcal{E}_2, \dots, \mathcal{E}_N\} \quad (18)$$

Furthermore, the services that can be provided by the MES to an energy carrier $\mathcal{E}_x \in \mathcal{E}$ are identified as $\{S = \{S_1, S_2, \dots, S_K\}\}_{\mathcal{E}_x}$, and each service $\{S_k\}_{\mathcal{E}_x}$ is defined by a set of static-parameters as:

$$\{S_k = \{t_k^a, t_k^d, \psi_k, p_k\}\}_{\mathcal{E}_x} \quad (19)$$

where, t_k^a/d , ψ_k , and p_k are the activation/deactivation time, call length and minimum power required for the service $\{S_k\}_{\mathcal{E}_x}$ available to energy carrier \mathcal{E}_x .

3.1. Two stage operational planning methodology

The methodology aims to optimize the operational planning of the plant, ensuring the satisfaction of the multi-energy demand and the MES participation in ancillary markets. The proposed methodology is composed of two stages, where the first stage minimizes MES operational cost in the energy market. The second stage then optimizes the provision of ancillary services by leveraging the MES flexibility while abiding the energy market commitment made by Stage-1. In more detail, the first stage takes day-ahead multi-energy demand profile and device parameters such as minimum/maximum power limits, conversion efficiencies, ramp rates, generation costs, etc., and optimally dispatch the different devices to satisfy the demand, while considering only the participation to energy markets. The second stage then takes the energy market commitment decided by Stage-1 and FCAS parameters such as full activation time, call length, etc., and computes the MES baseline, to optimally exploit the flexibility for the participation in ancillary service markets. The block diagram of the methodology is shown in Fig. 8. Both stages of the methodology are modelled as MILP and are detailed in the following Section 3.1. The methodology has been coded and solved using CPLEX© (IBM-ILOG).

3.2. Mathematical formulation

3.2.1. Objective function

The objective of Stage-1 is to optimize the participation of the MES in various energy markets while fulfilling multi-carrier demand(s) requirements and expressed as:

$$\mathcal{J}_1 = \underset{\Omega_1}{\text{minimize}} \sum_{\mathcal{E}_x \in \mathcal{E}} \left\{ \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \left(C^{\text{imp}} p_t^{\text{imp}} - \rho^{\text{exp}} p_t^{\text{exp}} + \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} C_g p_{g,t} - \sum_{d \in D} \rho^d p_{d,t} + C^\lambda \lambda_t \right) \right\}_{\mathcal{E}_x} \quad (20)$$

where t represents the time instance in the time horizon \mathcal{T} , and \mathcal{G} is the set of all energy conversion devices. The decision variables ($\Omega_1 = \{p_t^{\text{imp}}, p_t^{\text{exp}}, z_t^{\text{imp}}, p_{g,t}, p_{b,t}^+, p_{b,t}^-, z_{g,t}, u_{g,t}, d_{g,t}, \lambda_t\}$) consist on import (p_t^{imp}) and export (p_t^{exp}) power of the MES, dispatch ($p_{g,t}$), online status ($z_{g,t}$), start-up ($u_{g,t}$) and shutdown variable of individual conversion devices ($d_{g,t}$), charge/discharge power of storage ($p_{b,t}^{+/-}$) and load

curtailment (λ_t). Furthermore, C^{imp} and ρ^{exp} represent the energy import cost and energy export revenue of the MES, respectively, C_g is cost of energy conversion from device g , ρ^d , $p_{d,t}$ represent the revenue generated by fulfilling the demand and C^λ is the penalty for the unfulfilled demand (λ_t).

3.2.2. System constraints

The objective function is subjected to the following constraints:

Power balance: For each energy vector the import/export power ($p_t^{\text{imp/exp}}$) of the MES depends upon MES demand ($p_{d,t}$), power converted by devices ($p_{g,t}$), storage charge/discharge rate ($p_{b,t}^{+/-}$), demand shedding (λ_t), losses (ω_t), and expressed as:

$$\left\{ \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} p_{g,t} + \sum_{b \in B} (p_{b,t}^- - p_{b,t}^+) + p_t^{\text{imp}} + \lambda_t = \sum_{d \in D} p_{d,t} + p_t^{\text{exp}} + \omega_t \right\}_{\mathcal{E}_x} \quad (21)$$

Conversion device operational constraint: The operation of conversion device g that converts energy \mathcal{E}_y to \mathcal{E}_x is constrained by power limitation of each device (22), ramp up/down limitation (23), (27), their on/off status requirements (25), power lost during starting-up/shutting down phases (26), (25) and power converted between different energy vectors (28). In addition, the typical start and stop profile of a CHP plant is shown in Fig. 9 highlighting the amount of energy lost (grey area) during each phase (hereinafter when not needed energy layer is not explicitly specified). Furthermore, constraints (22)–(27) are applied for all energy layers interacting with conversion device g .

$$z_{g,t} p_g^- \leq p_{g,t} \leq z_{g,t} \bar{p}_g \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{G} \quad (22)$$

$$p_{g,t} - p_{g,t-\Delta t} \leq r_g^+ \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{G} \quad (23)$$

$$p_{g,t-\Delta t} - p_{g,t} \leq r_g^- \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{G} \quad (24)$$

$$u_{g,t} - d_{g,t} = z_{g,t} - z_{g,t-\Delta t} \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{G} \quad (25)$$

$$p_{g,t} = \hat{p}_{g,t} - u_{g,t} p_g^{\text{uloss}} \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{G} \quad (26)$$

$$p_{g,t} = \hat{p}_{g,t} - d_{g,t} p_g^{\text{dloss}} \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{G} \quad (27)$$

$$\{p_{g,t}\}_{\mathcal{E}_x} = \{p_{g,t}\}_{\mathcal{E}_y} \cdot \sigma_g^{\mathcal{E}_y, \mathcal{E}_x} + \alpha_g^{\mathcal{E}_y, \mathcal{E}_x} \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{G} \quad (28)$$

Storage constraint: The storage devices b in energy layer \mathcal{E}_x are subject to charge/discharge rate of the storage (29), (30), energy accumulation during interval length Δt (31) and storage limits (e_b/\bar{e}_b), (32). The binary variable $z_{b,t}^{+/-}$ represents the charging/discharging status of the storage and (33) ensures that a storage is either charging or discharging:

$$z_{b,t}^+ p_b^+ \leq p_{b,t}^+ \leq z_{b,t}^+ \bar{p}_b^+ \quad \forall b \in B \quad (29)$$

Fig. 9. Starting and stopping profiles of a real CHP, exemplify the amount of energy losses (grey area).

$$z_{b,t}^- p_b^- \leq p_{b,t}^- \leq z_{b,t}^- \bar{p}_b^- \quad \forall b \in B \quad (30)$$

$$e_{b,t+\Delta t} = e_{b,t} + \frac{p_{b,t}^+}{\eta_b^+} \Delta t - \eta_b^- p_{b,t}^- \Delta t - e_{b,t}^{\text{loss}} \quad \forall b \in B \quad (31)$$

$$\underline{e}_b \leq e_{b,t} \leq \bar{e}_b \quad \forall b \in B \quad (32)$$

$$z_{b,t}^+ + z_{b,t}^- \leq 1 \quad \forall b \in B \quad (33)$$

Maximum import/export limit: The power import/export of the MES is restricted by the connection limit for each energy vector $\mathcal{E}_x \in \mathcal{E}$, while ensuring that MES can either import power or export power at any given instance, governed by the binary variable z_t^{imp} :

$$\left\{ 0 \leq p_t^{\text{imp}} \leq z_t^{\text{imp}} \bar{p}^{\text{imp}} \right\}_{\mathcal{E}_x} \quad (34)$$

$$\left\{ 0 \leq p_t^{\text{exp}} \leq (1 - z_t^{\text{imp}}) \bar{p}^{\text{exp}} \right\}_{\mathcal{E}_x} \quad (35)$$

3.3. Second stage

The second stage aims at providing the best bids for the market services (in particular FCAS) that maximize their provision by exploiting the available flexibility while bounded by the energy market commitments ($p_t^{\text{imp}}/p_t^{\text{exp}}$) made by Stage-1. In Stage-2 the MES is allowed to turn on/off and change dispatch from different devices as long as the power exchange with the grid is not altered. Flexibility is then computed considering updated dispatch as base line, through the equations set in Section 2.4.

3.3.1. Objective function

The decision variables ($\{p_t^{\text{imp}}, p_t^{\text{exp}}, z_t^{\text{imp}}, \lambda_t\}$) obtained from the first stage of the methodology are then provided as input parameters to the second stage, while variables ($\Omega_2 = \{f_{S_k,t}^{\text{Ec},+/-}, p_{g,t}, z_{g,t}, u_{g,t}, d_{g,t}\}$) are used as decision variable for Stage-2. The outcome of this stage is the optimal scheduling of the resources in the ancillary service market, based on forecast of ancillary market prices deviation cost:

$$J_2 = \underset{\Omega_2}{\text{minimize}} \sum_{\mathcal{E}_x \in \mathcal{E}} \left\{ \sum_{t \in T} \left(\sum_{g \in G} C_g \Delta p_{g,t} - \sum_{k \in S_k} \rho_{S_k,t} f_{S_k,t}^{\text{Ec},+/-} \right) \right\}_{\mathcal{E}_x} \quad (36)$$

where $f_{S_k,t}^{\text{Ec}}$, $\rho_{S_k,t}$ and $\Delta p_{g,t}$ are the economic flexibility as explained in Section 2.4, market clearance price and power deviation for added additional flexibility, respectively. The terms $\sum_{g \in G} C_g \Delta p_{g,t}$ and

$\sum_{k \in S_k} \rho_{S_k,t} f_{S_k,t}^{\text{Ec},+/-}$ represent the cost of flexibility and revenues obtained through FCAS participation, respectively.

3.3.2. System constraints

The second stage objective function is subject to: the constraint (22)–(35), as used by Stage-1; economic flexibility constraints, as explained in Section 2.4, expressed by (4)–(15); and the plant-level constraints (37) and (38) to limit the MES imports and exports within the physical capacity limits of the relevant grids:

$$\left\{ \sum_{r \in R} f_{r,t}^{\text{Ec},-} + p_t^{\text{imp}} \leq z_t^{\text{imp}} \bar{p}^{\text{imp}} \right\}_{\mathcal{E}_x} \quad \forall \mathcal{E}_x \in \mathcal{E} \quad (37)$$

$$\left\{ \sum_{r \in R} f_{r,t}^{\text{Ec},+} + p_t^{\text{exp}} \leq (1 - z_t^{\text{imp}}) \bar{p}^{\text{exp}} \right\}_{\mathcal{E}_x} \quad \forall \mathcal{E}_x \in \mathcal{E} \quad (38)$$

4. Case study

4.1. General case study description

The two-stage optimization based on energy lattice framework is deployed to evaluate the participation of a gas-electricity-heat MES in the day-ahead and ancillary service markets, and its efficacy is demonstrated on a real-world case study based on Milan's district heating (DH) system. The case study is carried out in the context of European project MAGNITUDE (European project H2020 n. 774309). More specifically, the goal of the case study is to demonstrate and assess the techno-economic opportunities of the Milan DH system in providing frequency support ancillary services (FCAS) while also always satisfying the heat demand, and how this can be achieved by the plant leveraging its multi-energy flexibility. The study looks at typical European market structures and assesses the MES participation potential in i) Frequency Containment Reserve (FCR), ii) automatic Frequency Restoration Reserve (aFRR) and iii/iv) upward/downward manual Frequency Restoration Reserve (mFRR) as defined in [35] while specific requirements are inspired from the Italian regulation [36,37]. It should also be noted that the validation of the plant's technical ability to provide these market services under different condition has already been demonstrated in [38]. More specifically, the validation steps consisted of building a first order model of the plant, with hourly time resolution and weekly time horizon and verifying the satisfaction of the constraints set by each market service. In particular, the verification regards the real-time constraints set by the Italian regulatory framework [36] and by the Italian system operator [37].

4.2. Description of Milan DH system

The DH MES under study is a 3rd generation (see for a review on the evolution of district heating systems [39,40]) DH plant to supply the heat demand of the Milan municipality. The plant fulfils the DH heat demand by several multi-energy generation and storage technologies:

- gas-to-heat: three gas boiler (GB).

Fig. 10. Multi-energy interaction in Milan district heating plant, represented by the energy lattice. Gas energy layer (yellow) contains two conversion nodes (CHP and GB); electricity energy layer (blue) with three conversion nodes (CHP,HP and EB); heat energy layer (red) with four conversion nodes (GB, CHP, EB and HP) and the thermal storage (HS).

Table 1

Technical characteristics of the Milan DH plant’s multi-energy units. These information are taken from plant technical documentation, these parameters are needed by the methodology to configure the device models.

Device	Number of units	Electricity [MW _e]		Heat [MW _t]		Conversion efficiency or COP	Energy [MWh _t]	Start-up/shut down time [min]	Electrical ramp-rate (r _e) [MW _e /min]
		P _{min}	P _{max}	H _{min}	H _{max}				
CHP	3	2.5	5	2.75	4.76	0.43 (e) 0.41 (t)		15/15	0.25
HP	1	4.4	5.2	11.2	13	2.5		20/20	-
GB	3	0	0	0	16.1	0.93		10/10	-
EB	1	0.1	10.55	0.1	10.5	0.995		1/1	14
HS	2	0	0	0	11		29	-/-	-

- gas-to-heat-and-power: three combined heat and power (CHP) gas engines.
- power-to-heat: one water/water heat pump (HP), which exploits a geothermal source.
- power-to-heat: one electric boiler (EB).
- two heat storage (HS) units.

The heat storage helps to decouple heat production and demand supply. At the same time, the plant buys gas from the gas network and trades electricity on the day-ahead and intra-day markets. Fig. 10 represents the plant through the energy lattice framework. It is worth noting the representation of the different markets’ services on the gas and electricity layers, as also the district heating demand. The technical characteristics of the devices included in the plant are represented in Table 1. The plant can generate 15 MW_e of electricity locally and has maximum electricity demand of 13.75 MW_e out of which 10.55 MW_e is flexible load from EB while the maximum heat generation potential of the plant is 86 MW_t with 22 MW_t power provision capability from the thermal storage.

Heat is supplied to the end-users through a district heating network (about 90 km long, 45,000 nodes). The heat demand is distributed along the network across about 700 buildings, reaches a thermal peak of about 100 MW_t, and is composed of three different types of consumers, namely: residential (about 95%), and tertiary and commercial (2.5% each).

4.3. Consumption profile and market data

In order to limit analysis complexity in demonstrating the MES operation for an entire operating year, we have selected hourly resolution data for six representative weeks. Four of the six typical weeks data are representing each season (winter, spring, summer and autumn), while the other two weeks represent plant *critical* management conditions. The two extreme weeks, indicated as 1st-critical and 2nd-critical, are associated with the annual start and stop periods of DH demand, respectively. In these critical weeks, the heat demand shows a step change from lower to higher heat demand in the start week and vice-versa in the stop week. In the North of Italy these occur each October and April, respectively.

The plant operational management to meet the heat demand for a one-year horizon can be divided into three main operating strategies, each closely related to the annual seasons. These are *winter*, *mid-season* (i.e., autumn and spring), and *summer*, as represented in Fig. 11 with reference to the year 2019, and are associated with blue, red and green boxes, respectively. Furthermore, the orange arrow points to the DH stop period and the green one to the DH start period. As shown in Fig. 11, the winter programme impacts for 41% of the total time, the summer programme for 50%, and the mid-season one for 9%.

Market data related to the identified weeks is taken from the website of the Italian Market Operator [41]. These data include information for electricity and gas day-ahead markets and balancing market bids and outcomes for aFRR and mFRR upward and downward services. As the

Fig. 11. Heat daily peak demand throughout the year, and percentage duration of the three reference periods (winter, summer, mid-season).

Table 2

Main features of the ancillary service markets under study, as addressed in the MAGNITUDE project.

Service	FAT (r_k^a) [s]	p_k [MW _e]	Call length (ψ_k) [min]	Symmetric (yes/no)	$\bar{f}_{r,k}$ [MW _e] CHP	EB
FCR	30	0.375	60	yes	0.125	7
aFRR	200	1	60	yes	0.83	10.555
mFRR-up/dw	900	1	60	no	3.75	10.55

FCR service is not an established market product in Italy, relevant data for FCR are taken from the French electricity service market and scaled to be aligned with the Italian aFRR prices. The electricity and gas costs are aligned with the Italian regulation rr [42].

4.4. Ancillary services

The flexibility potential of the DH plant is exploited to provide FCR, aFRR, mFRR-up, and mFRR-dw based on the following features addressed in Section 2:

- MES/device ramp rate required to satisfy the service full activation time (FAT);
- Import/export and bi-directional service operating modes (including the special case of symmetric services); and
- Duration of the service provision.

Furthermore, only EB and CHP units are considered for FCAS participation, while the HP cannot provide its flexibility due to strict operating constraints on the water's geothermal source.

The FCAS considered for the study are derived from the most common European market structures as identified in [35]. These services are then revised to be compliant with the Italian regulation [36,37], as required by the MAGNITUDE project. Some of the salient characteristics of each service (S_k) are described in Table 2, with specific consideration for FAT (r_k^a), the minimum participation power requirement (p_k), and the call length (ψ_k) of each service. Additionally, Table 2 also details the maximum participation potential ($\bar{f}_{r,k}$) (restricted by their ramp rate and service FAT) of EB and CHP for each ancillary service market segment. Finally, Fig. 12 represents typical shape and temporal features of the different services.

4.5. Scenarios

The studies are organized into a number of scenarios to systematically analyse the Milan DH plant ability to supply the heat demand and provide multi-energy market and FCAS services. The following scenarios are considered to evaluate the impact of different FCAS participation:

- *Scenario-1*: the plant participates in the day-ahead energy markets and frequency containment reserve (FCR).

- *Scenario-2*: the plant's dispatch is co-optimized for day-ahead energy markets and automatic frequency restoration reserve (aFRR) service.
- *Scenario-3*: dispatch is co-optimized for day-ahead energy markets and downward manual frequency restoration reserve (mFRR-dw).
- *Scenario-4*: considers day-ahead energy markets and upward manual frequency restoration reserve (mFRR-up).
- *Scenario-5*: all FCAS that is FCR, aFRR, mFRR-up and mFRR-dw are considered along with the day ahead energy markets for co-optimized dispatch.

Furthermore, the Stage-1 in all scenarios represents the business as usual where the plant participates only in day ahead gas and electricity markets to satisfy the heat demand. In Stage-1, all the available heat storage (HS) capacity is used to manage heat demand requirements. Whereas, in Stage-2 63% of HS reserved for heat demand management and 37% being used for thermal flexibility provision to EB and CHP.

The first stage of methodology caters for energy balancing and energy market participation only, without provision of FCAS, and yield same results for the scenarios described above. On the other hand, the Stage-2 represent the optimal schedule of devices to supply the heat demand while participating in corresponding FCAS. A comparison of the different scenarios is summarized in Table 3.

4.6. Performance indicators

The different scenarios are assessed by means of the following key performance indicators:

- Economic indicators: MES operating costs and revenues.
- Technical indicators: flexibility availability.

The economic indicators are based on the variable costs to operate the MES to meet the baseline heat layer demand and on the additional fuels costs to increase or decrease the electricity output for the provision of energy and FCAS market services.

The technical indicators use the available and exploited flexibility for giving a measure of the suitability of the MES to provide grid services, based on the devices' upward and downward margins, as resulted in the different operating phases. Then, the difference between how much flexibility is available and actually deployed will depend on a number

Fig. 12. Shape and activation time constraints for frequency containment reserves (FCR), automatic frequency restoration reserves (aFRR), and upward and downward manual frequency restoration reserves (mFRR-up/dw).

Table 3
Market considered under each scenario set.

Scenarios	Electricity and gas energy markets	FCAS services traded Frequency containment reserve	Automatic frequency restoration reserve	Downward manual frequency restoration reserve	Upward manual frequency restoration reserve
Scenario-1	Yes	Yes	No	No	No
Scenario-2	Yes	No	Yes	No	No
Scenario-3	Yes	No	No	Yes	No
Scenario-4	Yes	No	No	No	Yes
Scenario-5	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

of factors, namely, the MES management strategy, the operating constraints, and the market arrangements and prices.

5. Results and discussions

5.1. Technical analysis

The commitment and dispatch results of the case study are presented in this section, which are obtained from the operational planning methodology presented in Section 3, for the scenarios introduced in Section 4.5. More specifically, the first stage of the methodology, which computes the plant day-ahead energy market participation is the same for all scenarios and yield similar results. The second stage then ensures the energy market commitment as decided by Stage-1, while optimising the flexibility margins to maximizes the FCAS participation revenues. On average a run of the two-stage methodology for each scenario took about 2 min.

The analysis of the technical performance is primarily focused on Scenario-5, as it covers plant participation in all FCAS (i.e., FCR, aFRR, mFRR-up/dw) for typical winter and summer weeks. The winter season presents the yearly highest heat demand and therefore higher flexibility margins. The summer season presents the yearly lowest heat demand, as highlighted in Fig. 11. In the discussion henceforth, power injected to an energy layer is taken as positive while the power consumption is considered negative.

5.1.1. Energy layer balancing

Let us first consider the winter week. Fig. 13 represents the dispatch of the DH plant devices to fulfil heat demand in Stage-1 (left) and Stage-2 (right) for Scenario-5. The cyan, grey, orange, green and blue areas represent the contribution of CHP units, HP, GB units, EB and HS, respectively, while the winter heat demand is shown by black line. The charging power of heat storage is represented along the negative axis, as it is withdrawing power from heat layer, and similarly the discharging of HS is taken as positive. In winter, the base heat load is met by CHP, HP and GB are contributing significantly as mid-level plants, while HS and EB are dispatched for peaking plants.

In Stage-1, heat demand is mostly provided by the CHP, HP, and GB. HS is dispatched to meet peak heat demand while the contribution from EB is negligible. The power generated by the CHP is primarily consumed by the HP and the remaining power is exported to the grid, as shown in Fig. 14 (left). Note that the power consumed by the EB is negligible. Stage-2 also consider the DH plant participation in FCAS markets and an increased dispatch from CHP and especially EB can be clearly observed from Fig. 13 (right), while the heat contribution of GB has been decreased. Simultaneous operation of EB and CHP is not an economically viable option if the DH plant is operating solely in energy markets. Indeed, in this case the electrical power generated by CHP is consumed by the EB and the overall efficiency of the plant would decrease. However, this operation allows the plant to control the operating point of CHP and EB and thus their upward and downward flexibility contribution (see Eqs. (4) and (5) and Section 2.4.2 for details). The cost of

Fig. 13. Dispatch of different DH plant resources to meet heat load demand in Stage-1 (left) and Stage-2 (right) for the typical winter week under Scenario-5.

Fig. 14. Electrical layer balance of DH plant in Stage-1 (left) and Stage-2 (right) for the typical winter week under Scenario-5.

Fig. 15. Dispatch of different DH plant resources to meet heat load demand under Scenario-5 (Stage-1 (left) and Stage-2 (right)) for the summer typical week.

operation is undoubtedly higher in Scenario-2, however, the revenue gained from participating in FCAS compensate the extra costs. The detailed cost analysis is further elaborated in Section 5.2.1. It is important to note in Stage-2 the excess power produced by the CHP is consumed by the EB and the power exchange with the grid remains the same. Furthermore, the increased heat power generated/consumed by CHP and EB in Stage-2 is balanced through reducing output from GB and HP.

The heat and electricity layer balancing profiles in summer week for Stage-1 (left) and Stage-2 (right) are given in Fig. 15 and Fig. 16, respectively. In the typical summer week, the heat demand profile is relatively smaller and resulted in vastly different heat and electrical dispatch pro-

files. As represented in Fig. 11 the average summer heat demand is more than ten times less than the winter one and heat demand for some intervals is almost zero. In contrast to the winter week, where most of the devices (HS, CHP, EB, GB and HP) are dispatched to meet heat requirement, in the summer week heat demand is mostly satisfied by CHP and HP in combination with HS in Stage-1, as shown in Fig. 15 (left). The power generated by the CHP is either consumed by the HP or exported to the grid. Besides, the electrical power demand of the plant is also negligible in the summer season. In Stage-2, increased activity is again observed for the EB, although in a limited capacity due to a smaller heat load profile. In comparison to Stage-1, the EB completely replaced the

Fig. 16. Electrical vector dispatch of DH plant in Stage-1 (left) and Stage-2 (right) for the summer week, under Scenario-5.

Fig. 17. Upward and downward flexibility potential of the DH plant (blue lines) against flexibility contribution from CHP (cyan) and EB (green) under Scenario-5 after Stage-1 (left) and Stage-2 (right) for the winter week.

electricity consumption of HP and thus the resultant heat deficit is fulfilled by the GB (see Fig. 16 (right)). Note that the electricity exchange with the grid in Stage-1 and Stage-2 is the same. Henceforth, the technical analysis is focused on the winter week due to the large flexibility potential, nevertheless, general conclusion for all the typical weeks are identical.

5.1.2. Electrical flexibility

The operational flexibility (see Section 2.4.2) available to electrical vector in winter after Stage-1 and Stage-2 is shown in Fig. 17. The upward flexibility is represented along the positive y-axis and downward flexibility is represented along the negative y-axis. In Stage-1, the plant is optimized for the energy market participation only, and the resultant operational flexibility is shown in Fig. 17 (left), where CHP is mostly providing upward flexibility and contribute very little towards downward flexibility, and on contrary, the EB is mostly providing downward flexibility. Therefore, most of the time the plant is unable to offer either CHP or EB flexibility to the markets with symmetric requirement (i.e., FCR and aFRR). In Stage-2, the plant is co-optimized for energy and FCAS participation, and CHP and EB are optimally dispatched to contribute towards flexibility services, as shown in Fig. 17 (right).

The DH plant participation potential for FCR (top row), aFRR (middle row) and mFRR (bottom row) markets is shown for Scenario-5 after Stage-1 (left column) and Stage-2 (right column) in Fig. 18. The upward flexibility potential is shown along the positive y-axis while the downward flexibility potential is shown along the negative y-axis. Note that the FCR and aFRR participation potential after Stage-1 is negligible, as Stage-1 is optimized for energy markets and not the FCAS. However, the plant has the potential to participate in mFRR-up/dw services by deploying flexibility potential from CHP and EB, respectively, as shown in Fig. 18 (right column, bottom row).

The ability of the methodology to maximize the amount of flexibility to provide FCAS goes beyond the identification of suitable services for

available flexibility. The methodology, in fact, also allows an optimal schedule of the flexibility that each device could provide in order to exploit the greatest possible amount of flexibility. To this aim let us consider the schedule of each ancillary service after Stage-2 presented in Fig. 18, one by one.

The FCR results of Stage-2 for winter are shown in Fig. 18 (top row, right column), illustrating the participation potential of EB (green), and CHP (cyan). Note that CHP participation in FCR market is limited because of its slower ramp rate and market FAT requirement of 30s. Resultantly, FCR is dominantly provided by the EB with a fast ramp rate, thus explaining the uneconomical simultaneous operation of CHP and EB, as previously discussed in Section 5.1.1.

It is also worth noting that the algorithm computes different levels of contributions from EB and CHP units to provide symmetric services, exploiting as much flexibility as possible for each device. Fig. 18 (middle row, right column) shows aFRR profile set. The CHP have relatively more time to ramp up/down for aFRR market with FAT of 200s, thus each unit of CHP is able to provide a maximum of 0.83 MW_e each. Resultantly, more flexibility contribution from the CHP can be seen for aFRR then FCR.

The electrical flexibility potential for mFRR markets is the largest among the considered services (see Fig. 18 (bottom row, right column) because it has the relatively higher FAT of 900s and no symmetric requirement.

5.1.3. Role of carrier-balancing flexibility

The carrier-balancing flexibility enables deployment of FCAS services by relying on flexibility made available from energy layers other than electricity. In particular, the GB and HS units act as the backup of CHP and EB units and inject/absorb heat imbalance generated due to the CHP and EB participation in the FCAS. Thus, indirectly enabling provision of operational electrical flexibility through the concept of carrier balancing flexibility. The heat layer balancing capability of GB and HS

Fig. 18. FCR (top row), aFRR (middle row) and mFRR (bottom row) participation potential of the plant after Stage-1 (left column) and Stage-2 (right column) for winter typical week under Scenario-5.

Fig. 19. Scenario-5 winter week: maximum amount of upward (left) downward (right) heat compensation required to balance the ancillary service provisions at Stage-2.

units, while CHP and EB provide FCAS, is represented in Fig. 19 (left) (upward heat balance) and Fig. 19 (right) (downward heat balance). More specifically, the graph in Fig. 19 (left) illustrates the (maximum) upward heat unbalancing due to EB (green) and CHP (cyan) operation to provide upward electrical flexibility services. The orange and blue areas in this graph represent the successful balancing action on the heat energy layer from GB and HS units which completely make up for the upward unbalancing. Similarly, in the graph of Fig. 19 (right) the maximum downward heat unbalancing due to EB (green) and CHP (cyan) electricity-related operation, and the orange and blue area represent the successful balancing action due to GB and HS units.

Fig. 20 illustrates all FCAS, namely, FCR, aFRR, mFRR-up, and mFRR-dw that are traded in the market for Scenario-5. The upward flexibility is shown along positive y-axis and downward flexibility along negative y-axis. The blue and orange shadowed areas depict the plant available upward and downward electrical flexibility, respectively, and

the blue and brown dashed lines represent the available heat flexibility (the heat upward flexibility is actually too high to be represented in the graph). The ability of the methodology to optimally schedule different services while accounting for the different operational constraint is evident from Fig. 20. Note that FCAS participation is limited by the downward heat flexibility envelope. For example, during intervals 22–30 the plant has the capability to participate in all three services (as shown in Fig. 18 (right column)), however, the GB and HS are not able to make up for the heat capacity and thus plant electrical flexibility provision is limited due to the lack of heat layer flexibility.

5.2. Performance analysis

This section, report and discuss the aggregated results concerning the plant’s economic performance. For each scenario, the results are taken in aggregate form for each representative week.

Fig. 20. Scenario-5 typical winter week: market services scheduled by the second stage of the methodology.

Fig. 21. (Left) operational costs and revenues obtained from Stage-1 and Stage-2 of the methodology. (Right) net operating cost of the plant under various scenarios for typical weeks.

5.2.1. Costs and revenues

The plant operation cost (sum of all the cost from Stage-1 and Stage-2) and FCAS revenue (obtained from the second stage of the methodology) for six typical weeks, under all scenarios are presented along the positive and negative y-axis in Fig. 21 (left), respectively. Besides, the Stage-1 operational cost, which is the same in all scenarios, is also reported in Fig. 21. The Stage-1 operational cost aggregately shows the fuel (natural gas) and electricity day-ahead market participation (for purchase and sale) cost, for each typical week. The operational cost in Fig. 21 (left) includes the cost of energy market participation cost (as provided by Stage-1) plus cost incurred to redispatch resources for flexibility maximisation (at Stage-2). Furthermore, the net operational cost (i.e., cost minus revenue) is shown in Fig. 21 (right).

From Fig. 21 (left), the operational cost of Stage-1 for all the typical weeks is lowest as it only optimizes participation in the energy markets. However, it generates no revenues from the FCAS and consequently has the highest net operational cost as shown in Fig. 21 (right). The highest net operational cost of Stage-1 reflects that the plant is better-off with participation in any FCAS as this would result in revenues from FCAS and hence a lower net operational cost. The results well highlight how the methodology maximizes participation in multiple market services gaining relevant economic benefits. In particular, Scenario-5 (where flexibility is optimized in all FCAS) has resulted in minimum net operational costs for all typical weeks. Thus, it is possible to leverage the most performing devices in order to maximize the amount of flex-

ibility devoted to providing services. However, at the same time, the comparison highlights as in many scenarios, to get the greatest benefits from the FCAS, higher redispatch result in higher operational cost than Scenario-1. For example, the Scenario-5 has the least net operational cost across all typical weeks, however, it also has the highest operational cost, which is matched by the highest revenues, as shown by Fig. 21 (right).

Noting that the Scenarios-1–4 represent the plant participation in one market at a time and Scenario-5 considers participation in all FCAS, simultaneously, the main messages coming from these results are: (i) the optimal redispatch of base-line to better exploit flexibility for introduce extra-costs for plant operation, this cost is then recovered from revenues; (ii) the least profit is generated in Scenario-1 where the plant is participating in FCR (most constrained service) market alone; (iii) the most revenues are generated from mFRR-up service, this is mainly due to fewer constraints; and (iv) although the profits during the summer season are relatively small, however, given that the summer season lasts for six months and spans over 50.4% of the year, the impact cannot be overlooked.

5.2.2. Flexibility analysis: availability and deployment

This section aims to highlight the efficacy of the plant under analysis to provide flexibility to the power system by looking at the available operational flexibility and economic flexibility metrics (see Section 2.4). More specifically, Fig. 22 shows the amount of flexibility

Fig. 22. Percentage of available upward and downward flexibility deployed as market service in the different scenarios.

exploited, against the available one, for each scenario in the different seasons.

Upward flexibility. The positive values in the y-axis of the graph in Fig. 22 illustrate the ability of the plant to exploit the upward available flexibility. In winter the algorithm leverages more than 60% of the available flexibility in all scenarios, and for Scenario-4 (mFRR-up participation) (green bars) this value is 80%. In the other typical weeks, the Scenario-4 and Scenario-5 present the highest amount of exploited upward flexibility: in spring this is 80%, and even more than 90% in summer.

Downward flexibility. The negative values in the y-axis of the graph in Fig. 22 show the deployment of the downward flexibility. Comparing the positive and the negative parts of the graph, that is comparing the exploitation of upward and downward available flexibility, respectively, the percentage of downward flexibility exploited is always less appreciated than the upward one because of the lower prices for downward services. In any season, the Scenario-3 (purple bars) greatly exploits downward flexibility. In summer season, no scenario achieves a significant amount of downward flexibility exploitation, this is primarily due to the lack of flexibility on the heat carrier.

6. Concluding remarks

In this paper we have proposed a novel modelling framework and an associated optimization tool to support multi-energy system (MES) short-term operational planning and electricity market service trading. The framework is tailored to deploy flexibility with specific application to provision of frequency control ancillary services (FCAS). The modelling framework proposed is based on the concept of multi-energy lattice to represent a MES by several energy layers, each one associated to a specific energy carrier and linked together by conversion nodes. The operational optimization methodology associated with the framework is based on a two-step MILP formulation. More specifically, the first step ensures adequate supply of the local network heat demand and the acquisition of relevant gas resources on the day-ahead gas market. At the same time, day-ahead electricity market is accessed to import electricity in deficit periods and export electricity in the surplus ones. The available flexibility margins resulting from the first step is then deployed in the second step to maximize the profitability of the plant to provide different FCAS, namely, frequency containment regulation (FCR), automatic frequency restoration reserve (aFRR) and manual frequency restoration reserve (mFRR). Moreover, a new categorization of the available flexibility margins in the context of multi-energy systems, and consistent with the features of the multi-energy lattice framework, has been proposed. This categorization can provide clear insights in supporting the

assessment of MES flexibility provision with respect to satisfaction of the relevant multi-energy demand, system constraints, and market rules. A real-world case study based on the Milan district heating plant has been studied, with the support of real technical and market data to demonstrate the ability of the methodology to trade multiple services at the same time, both in the case of symmetric and non-symmetric products, and subject to very different temporal constraints and market requirements.

Future work aims at extending the methodology to more applications spread across energy networks, enabling the ability to deal with uncertainty, to fully model and capture the flexibility available in distributed multi-energy systems [13] and quantify their system technical and economic value.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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